

Frequency and Level dependence of the middle ear acoustic reflex and its decay measured in wideband absorbance with contralateral narrowband noise elicitors.

Abbie Baricevich, Danielle Bassett, Sophia Chan, Shayna Lavi, and Jonathan Siegel ^{a)}

^{a)}*Department of Communication Sciences and Disorders; Hugh Knowles Center, Northwestern University.*

^{a)}j-siegel@northwestern.edu

Abstract. The acoustic reflex has shown promise to identify individuals with selective damage to cochlear sensory neurons (5, 9, 23). If damage to neurons is localized, then using broadband stimuli to elicit the reflex, as reported in the studies cited above, may not be most effective in revealing spatially restricted lesions. We have measured changes in admittance with chirps delivered to one ear and contralateral narrowband noise to elicit the reflex. We aim to characterize the frequency and level dependence of changes in admittance elicited by noise with different center frequencies as well as the decay of the reflex for prolonged elicitors as a baseline for comparison with similar measurements in individuals suspected of having neural damage. Our hypothesis is that elicitors that preferentially activate the damaged part of the reflex pathway will show the largest deviation from normal. We have identified a novel sensitization of the acoustic reflex following repeated exposure to moderate level elicitors such that absorbance changes more than double, regardless of the level of the elicitor, compared with the minimally stimulated contralateral ear. These changes recover slowly. We are measuring the growth of the reflex vs elicitor level and at constant elicitor level vs center frequency. We are also measuring the rate of reflex decay vs elicitor center frequency. Preliminary findings substantiate the measurement protocols in revealing differences between individuals and ears.

INTRODUCTION

The reflex contraction of the stapedius muscle has been applied to assessing its auditory function (3) and diagnosing retrocochlear lesions (2) and has generally been seen as the effect of a simple reflex arc. It can be evoked by stimulating either ear. In our experiments we assess the effect of the contraction by measuring the change in admittance in one ear caused by presenting the eliciting sound to the contralateral ear. While the function of the acoustic reflex is not known definitively, its greatest effect is to reduce transmission of sound to the inner ear at low frequencies. This likely reduces their effect on masking of behaviorally important higher frequencies (4, 19). The stapedius muscle is composed primarily of Type II muscle fibers that are capable of fast and prolonged contractions (17). The neural circuitry has been characterized extensively (14). While inputs from various brain regions to the stapedius motoneurons have been documented anatomically, their potential modulatory influences are not known.

Sensitive wideband measures of the acoustic reflex (middle ear muscle reflex or MEMR) demonstrate activation by acoustic stimuli as low as 60 dB SPL and the strength of the reflex increases with the level of the elicitor (7-9). One promising application of the MEMR is to detect the presence of cochlear synaptopathy, which may be detected by changes in the strength of the reflex (5, 9, 23). Since synaptopathy might be localized in specific regions of the cochlea, we were interested in exploring the frequency and level dependence of the acoustic reflex, reasoning that this might make it easier to identify the region of damage. We report our initial efforts to characterize the essential aspects of the MEMR in normal hearing human participants, exploring the effects of the level, spectrum and duration of

contralateral elicitors. Our unanticipated finding that the strength of the acoustic reflex can vary considerably with time and prior stimulation suggests that we are engaging descending inputs to the stapedius motoneurons, suggesting that the reflex adapts to the varying intensity of environmental sound.

METHODS

Wideband Absorbance

The Etymotic Research ER-10X probe system was used to measure changes in absorbance by the ear, calculated from the pressure response in the ear canal (P_{ec}) to ~70 dB SPL wideband chirps. The probe source calibrations and in-ear calibrations were performed using EMAV (18) The probe was calibrated in a motorized calibrator and the source pressure (P_{src}) and impedance (Z_{src}) were calculated as described previously (1, 6, 11, 20, 21).

The acoustic impedance of the ear (Z_{ec}) was calculated using the ear canal pressure and the stored probe calibration parameters:

$$Z_{ec} = \frac{Z_{src}P_{ec}}{P_{src} - P_{ec}} \quad (1)$$

The pressure reflectance was calculated from the ear canal impedance, where the characteristic impedance of the ear canal is denoted as Z_0 :

$$R_p = \frac{Z_{ec} - Z_0}{Z_{ec} + Z_0} \quad (2)$$

Lastly, the power absorbance was calculated from the pressure reflectance:

$$Abs = 1 - R_p^2 \quad (3)$$

The elicitor used to induce the MEMR was either wideband or 1/3 octave-band random noise generated by a sound source calibrated in an ear simulator (B&K 60318-4). The source was coupled to the ear canal using 18 ga tubing and fitted with a conventional ear-tip. The measured levels were then controlled by a software controlled digital attenuator. The change in absorbance induced by elicitor was calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the presence of the elicitor from the absorbance with no elicitor. The change in absorbance over a wide frequency band was calculated at the total rms change in the band from 0.2 - 4 kHz. Our measures of the MEMR are consistent with previous reports of changes in wideband absorbance using click stimuli (7-9).

Behavioral Thresholds

Behavioral thresholds for pure tones in quiet were measured at one-third octave intervals between 0.25 and 8 kHz using a modified Békésy tracking procedure (15). Threshold stimulus levels were expressed as eardrum SPL estimated by summing the magnitude of the forward and reverse pressures in the participant's ear canal (16). Consent was obtained from human participants and we followed a protocol approved by the Institutional Review Board of Northwestern University.

RESULTS

One of our early findings was that the repeated presentation of a moderate-level elicitor often caused a strengthening of the acoustic reflex (Fig. 1). It was convenient to reduce the magnitude of the change in admittance vs frequency to a single number, representing an RMS measure of the change in admittance over a band of frequencies (typically 0.2 – 4 kHz).

FIGURE 1. Absorbance change induced by the MEMR as a function of frequency (a). The baseline measure (blue) was collected at the beginning of the test session and the change was 0.12 RMS absorbance units. The red curve (0.3 units RMS) was collected following repeated exposures to an 80 dB SPL 1/3 octave band of noise centered at 1 kHz at the times shown (b). Following 35 minutes of intermittent repeat measurement of the MEMR, the strength of the reflex had not returned to baseline (red circle and arrow).

Although repeated presentation of the elicitor most frequently causes an increase in the strength of the MEMR, it could weaken in some cases. Furthermore, recovery from the adapted condition varied considerably between participants (Fig. 2). Behavioral thresholds measured using Békésy tracking and referenced to estimated eardrum pressure (not shown) changed by only a few dB and were not related to the changes in MEMR absorbance.

FIGURE 2. Adaptation can increase or decrease below baseline in different participants and times after repeated presentations of the elicitor. (a) Enhancement of the magnitude of the MEMR is not only evident immediately following the initial exposure (red curve). It continues to increase in magnitude even during one hour of silence (yellow curve). The enhancement approaches 10 dB in this example. (b) We sometimes measured considerable decline in the magnitude of the MEMR at long times after noise-induced enhancement was observed, in this case 3.5 hours after the repeated elicitor presentations. This result might mean that the reflex of this participant was already enhanced at the beginning of the experiment, possibly because of exposure beforehand to uncontrolled environmental sounds.

We had been measuring the dependence MEMR on the level of the elicitor systematically from near threshold to the highest level under study (typically 90 dB SPL), but it was suggested to the last author by John Guinan that he had

observed hysteresis of the reflex activation in previous work (10). Accordingly, we replaced our conditioning exposures to the elicitor with a series of measures from the lowest to the highest elicitor level and back down. Hysteresis was consistently observed from the first downward series following the first upward series (Fig 3).

FIGURE 3. Hysteresis in MEMR dependence on elicitor level. (a) Sensitization of the reflex develops during repeated upward runs of elicitor level (solid curves). For each upward run, the absorbance change is consistently larger during the downward runs, beginning at the first one (dashed curves). (b) Hysteresis is evident when all ascending and descending runs are averaged.

One of our primary interests is to explore the activation of the MEMR by 1/3 octave random noise centered at frequencies ranging from 0.5 to 10 kHz. An efficient paradigm maintained the level of the noise constant at 80 dB SPL as a measure of the dependence of the reflex on the frequency of the elicitor. The strongest activation of the reflex was generally for elicitors in the range of 1-3 kHz, but activation was seen for frequencies as high as 8 kHz. The strength of activation with different noise frequencies was generally much weaker for frequencies above 2 kHz. Enhancement of the reflex following adaptation was also generally greatest for frequencies below 4 kHz.

FIGURE 4. Example of the dependence of MEMR absorbance change on the center frequency of 1/3 octave band noise at 80 dB SPL. As for other measures, the strength of the reflex was enhanced following adaptation to conditioning with repeated presentation of wideband noise. Enhancement generally declined at higher elicitor frequencies. The change is presented as a ratio in dB (right axis).

We have also begun to explore the decline in the strength of the reflex (reflex decay) by presenting the elicitor for varying durations before the second measurement of ear canal impedance. Following a conditioning exposure to 80 dB SPL WBN, reflex decay was measured using 1/3 octave-band noise centered at 1, 2 and 4 kHz at 90 dB SPL. Here again, the patterns varied within and between participants, with some trends exhibiting monotonic decline in absorbance and others showing nonmonotonicities (Fig. 5). Repeating measurements is an important means of

assuring stability and repeatability, but the extent of repeatability may be limited by the accumulating recent history of exposure to the strong elicitor. Still, the agreement between subsequent tests in the same test session in Fig. 5 is encouraging. The wide-band measurement was sensitive enough to follow the trends at all three elicitor frequency bands. Lowering the level of the elicitor while still making useful measurements seems possible.

FIGURE 5. Change in absorbance with increasing duration of the 90 dB SPL elicitor. The strength of the reflex generally showed a gradual decline with increasing duration, but some nonmonotonicities were noted. The dashed lines in (b) are repeat measurements made in the same test session immediately following the first set of measurements.

DISCUSSION

Activation of the middle ear acoustic reflex was studied by measuring the change in wideband admittance in ears of human participants in response to moderate-level noise elicitors of the reflex. The measurements for each condition achieved good signal to noise ratio with only around ten seconds required to measure the ear canal acoustic impedance and absorbance by itself alone and again in the presence of a contralateral elicitor. Part of this speed was due to the use of wide-band chirps to calculate absorbance from the measured pressure response. As reported previously, the threshold of the wideband MEMR for wideband elicitors is typically ~ 60 dB SPL (7-9). We have noted that this threshold is remarkably consistent for participants with normal hearing thresholds, which are typically more than 40 dB lower than the threshold for the wideband MEMR (Figs. 2-3).

The magnitude of the reflex was typically found to grow stronger during repeated presentations of the elicitor, but could also be enhanced by the binaural stimulation used to measure the reflex without additional presentations of the elicitor (Figs. 1-4). Behavioral thresholds, measured using Békésy tracking, showed no consistent increase in hearing sensitivity comparable to the enhancement of the MEMR and were much smaller than the changes in the strength of the reflex. This supports the interpretation that the afferent pathways that determine the threshold sensitivity to tonal stimuli are not the origin of the enhancement of the MEMR. Rather, the enhancement appears to originate in the efferent part of the stapedial reflex circuitry, again possibly due to activation of one or more modulatory inputs to the stapedius motoneurons and/or in the stapedius muscle itself. The enhancement of the reflex could be observed for several hours after being induced, but eventually dissipated over time with a highly variable time-course that varied between participants. But decreases in the reflex below baseline could also be measured in some participants and several hours after the adapting exposures to the elicitor. These changes over long time periods are most likely caused by central modulation than changing properties of the stapedius muscle or of the motor end-plate synapses. Pronounced hysteresis of the reflex, depending on the direction of change in elicitor levels (Fig 3), may have a different origin than the other long-term gain changes, possibly originating in the muscle itself or its motor innervation.

Large changes were observed in absorbance from the MEMR as the center frequency of the elicitor was changed (Fig. 4). This is noteworthy given the demonstration of broad tuning curves of cat stapedius motoneurons (12). They reported that these motoneurons receive inputs from a wide range of cochlear locations. This is understandable, since the action of the stapedius is to vary the strength of contraction to regulate the amount of absorption of sound by the ear, not to change the absorption in a frequency-dependent way. However, the threshold sensitivity of most of the neurons in the Kobler et al study was appreciably higher than the electromyography (EMG) threshold for the muscle itself or the ~ 60 dB SPL MEMR threshold we see in awake humans. There are strikingly different numbers of stapedius muscle fibers innervated by different motoneurons and this is likely part of how different motor units are

recruited in controlling the strength of contraction in response to a large range of sound levels (22). Further study is needed to account for the sensitivity and dynamics of the reflex.

We have also begun to study the change in absorbance from the MEMR as a function of the duration of the elicitor before the second measurement of the absorbance in the ipsilateral ear (reflex decay, Fig. 5). The wideband approach to measuring the MEMR seems quite sensitive and optimal to measure reflex decay as a function of the frequency of the elicitor. The large variation in decay in different participants and elicitor noise band center frequencies does not appear to be due to variability in measurement, though this must be confirmed experimentally by evaluating reproducibility within and across test sessions in individual participants.

The enhancement of the MEMR may contribute to optimizing hearing in noisy environments, primarily by attenuating low-frequency transmission of potentially masking sounds (4, 19). This change appears to parallel the sensitization of the medial olivocochlear efferent system in anesthetized guinea pigs reported previously (13). They reported that sensitization developed over 2-3 minutes, which is similar to examples shown here for the MEMR in awake humans. That the strength of the MEMR can also decline below our baseline measurement at prolonged times implies that the individual exposures to typical environmental sounds before the experiment was likely. This would be expected if the function of the MEMR is to optimize hearing in changing levels of environmental sound.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Supported by Northwestern University.

REFERENCES

1. J. B. Allen, "Measurement of eardrum acoustic impedance," in *Peripheral Auditory Mechanisms*, edited by JB Allen, JL Hall, A Hubbard, ST Neely, and A Tubis, Springer-Verlag, New York, pp. 44–51 (1981).
2. H. Anderson, B. Barr and E. Wedenberg, "Intra-aural reflexes" in retrocochlear lesions. pp. 49-55. in C. A. Hamberger and I. Wersall. eds. *Disorders of the Skull Base Region*. Almqvist & Wiksell. Stockholm. Sweden (1969).
3. E. Borg, "On the use of acoustic middle ear muscle reflexes in studies of auditory function in nonanesthetized rabbits." *Acta Oto-Laryngologica*, **74**, 240-247 (1972).
4. E. Borg and J. E. Zakrisson, "Stapedius reflex and monaural masking." *Acta Oto-Laryngologica*, **78**, 155-161 (1974).
5. N. F. Bramhall, K. M. Reavis, M. P. Feeney and S. D. Kampel, "The impacts of noise exposure on the middle ear muscle reflex in a veteran population." *Am J Audiol* **31**, 126–142 (2022).
6. B. L. Farmer-Fedor and R. D. Rabbitt, "Acoustic intensity, impedance and reflection coefficient in the human ear canal," *J Acoust Soc Am* **112**, 600–620 (2002).
7. M. P. Feeney and D. H. Keefe, "Estimating the acoustic reflex threshold from wideband measures of reflectance, admittance, and power," *Ear Hear* **22**, 316-332 (2001).
8. M. P. Feeney, D. H. Keefe, L. L. Hunter, D. F. Fitzpatrick, A. C. Garinis, D. B. Putterman and G. P. McMillan, "Normative wideband reflectance, equivalent admittance at the tympanic membrane, and acoustic stapedius reflex threshold in adults." *Ear Hear* **38**, e142ee160 (2017).
9. M. P. Feeney, K. S. Schairer and D. B. Putterman, "Wideband acoustic reflex measurement," *Sem Hearing* **44**, 84-92 (2023).
10. J. J. Guinan Jr, (private communication. 2024).
11. D. H. Keefe, R. Ling and J. C. Bulen, "Method to measure acoustic impedance and reflection coefficient," *J Acoust Soc Am* **91**, 470–485 (1992).
12. J. B. Kobler, J. J. Guinan Jr., S. R. Vacher and B. E. Norris, "Acoustic reflex frequency selectivity in single stapedius motoneurons of the cat." *Journal of Neurophysiology*, **68**, 807–817 (1992).
13. E. Larsen and M. C. Liberman, "Slow build-up of cochlear suppression during sustained contralateral noise: Central modulation of olivocochlear efferents?" *Hearing Res* **256**, 1-10 (2009).
14. D. J. Lee, T. E. Benson and M. C. Brown, "Diverse synaptic terminals on rat stapedius motoneurons." *Journal of the Association for Research in Otolaryngology* **9**, 321-333 (2008).
15. J. Lee, S. Dhar, R. Abel, R. Banakis, E. Grolley, J. Lee, S. Zecker and J. Siegel, "Behavioral hearing thresholds between 0.125 and 20 kHz using depth-compensated ear simulator calibration," *Ear Hear*. **33**, 315-329 (2012).
16. J. D. Lewis, R. W. McCreery, S. T. Neely and P. G. Stelmachowicz, "Comparison of in situ calibration method for quantifying input to the middle ear," *J Acoust Soc Am* **126**, 3114–3124 (2009).

17. M. J. Lyon and L. T. Malmgren, "A histochemical characterization of muscle fiber types in the middle ear muscles of the cat. I. The stapedius muscle." *Acta Oto-Laryngologica*, **94**, 99-109 (1982).
18. S. T. Neely and Z. Liu, "EMAV: Otoacoustic emission averager," Technical Memo No. 17 Omaha, NE, Boys Town National Research Hospital (1994).
19. X. D. Pang and J. J. Guinan Jr, "Effects of stapedius-muscle contractions on the masking of auditory-nerve responses," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **102**, 3576–3586 (1997).
20. R. A. Scheperle, S. T. Neely, J. G. Kopun and M. P. Gorga, "Influence of in situ, sound-level calibration on distortion-product otoacoustic emission variability," *J Acoust Soc Am* **124**, 288–300 (2008).
21. N. N. Souza, S. Dhar, S. T. Neely and J. H. Siegel, "Comparison of nine methods to estimate ear-canal stimulus levels," *J Acoust Soc Am* **136**, 1768–1787 (2014).
22. S. R. Wiener-Vacher, J. J. Guinan, Jr., J. B. Kobler, and B. E. Norris, "Motoneuron axon distribution in the cat stapedius muscle." *Hearing Research*, **133**, 139-148 (1999).
23. M. Wojtczak, J. A. Beim and A. J. Oxenham, "Weak middle-ear-muscle reflex in humans with noise-induced tinnitus and normal hearing may reflect cochlear synaptopathy." *eNeuro*, **4**, ENEURO.0363-17.2017. (2017).

REFERENCES AND DISCUSSION

[Anders Fridberger] Comment. So we're talking about striated muscles here, so could you imagine a training program for the middle ear reflex. If you do this repeatedly every day your muscles would become bigger and stronger and perhaps there would be some benefits to that if you have to listen in noise.

[Jonathan Siegel] Answer. Well yes, anything's possible. I think you're right. I get a sense that my middle ear muscles are stronger after being a subject. When my students were away (on break) I was the only one around who could do the measurement. But I don't have a reflex that is stronger than any of my younger colleagues, so there's a limit.

[Christopher Bergevin] Comment. Your point at the beginning "means to probe central control" is well taken. I was curious about the role of attention. Did you give people a task to focus their attention on and does that have any sort of effect?

[Jonathan Siegel] Answer. I've done just a little of that but so far we haven't found anything, but that is definitely something we want to look into. Absolutely.

[Harry Bharadwaj] Comment. We're very interested in the reflex for diagnostic purposes as you mentioned in the beginning. So when we have done studies with this and look at measures of variability and when we test people at different times they tend to rank similarly across the different measurements. So even though there's some variability from test to test, someone with a big reflex generally has a big reflex and someone with a small reflex... So (I'd like) to understand how big is the sensitization effect related to differences in the baseline.

[Jonathan Siegel] Answer. We have done some repeat measurements on individuals and I would agree with your assessment. If we get a large reflex or a large sensitization the first time then we'll get it the next time as well. It occasionally goes in the opposite direction so that's where questions like attention and other tasks that we might be doing come into play.